

Preparation of bone of Rhesus monkey (*Macaca mulatta*) without use of Chemical

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Abstract

Skeleton is frame work of hardest structure which support and protect the soft tissue of animal body. The bones of the animals help in identification of animal in forensic anatomy. This study will be help full to the wildlife veterinarian in diseases control regime.

Introduction

Specimen, Cadavers and organs are essential for the study of anatomy, pathology and forensic medicine in medical, veterinary, ayurveda and allied health sciences. With the emergence of super specialisations in medical sciences like gastroenterology, cardiovascular surgeries, hepatobiliary surgeries, renal transplant, paediatrics surgeries, neurosurgery etc. detailed anatomical knowledge is needed for recent application in clinical sciences. Preservation is an action to keep some things safe from harm, destruction or decomposition, conservation is defined as the process of a careful preservation and protection of some things. Bones of Rhesus monkey were prepared without using chemical, which were toxic to the environment. This study will be helpful to the forensic anatomist for interpretation of bones of human and rhesus monkey. Since, there is very scanty work on preparation of bones of Rhesus monkey without using chemical; hence the present study was designed.

Brief Methodology

Removal of the visceral organs and maximum number of skeletal muscles of the Rhesus monkey

(Fig.1) to be preserved. After removal of skeletal muscles from the body of the animal (Fig.2), kept animal in water for purification for 6 days. When the animal was putrefied then maggot was formed which ate the remaining muscles of the bone. Then, the bones of the animals removed from the water tank and washed thoroughly in running tap water. After washing, the bones were kept in tray (Fig.3) for sun drying.

Fig.1. Photograph showing the Rhesus monkey (*Macaca mulatta*)

Fig.2. Photograph showing the Rhesus monkey (*Macaca mulatta*) after removal skin and skeletal muscles.

Fig.3. Photograph showing the bones of Rhesus monkey (*Macaca mulatta*) in tray.

Conclusion

It will helpful in forensic anatomy for comparison of bones of human and Rhesus monkey. It will also helpful biologist to study about the taxidermy of the animals and preservation of the precious animals.

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